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A Dynamic Production Programming Approach with Artificial Intelligence Techniques within the Framework of Industry 4.0: The Case of Elevator Industry

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ABSTRACT

Order management is of great importance for today's businesses. Timely and complete delivery of orders increases customer satisfaction and makes production planning critical. At this point, it is necessary to have a good production plan to manage orders. This study examines the production process at an elevator company that manufactures products based on customer requests. Since the production process has a dynamic structure, the company has shifted toward a flexible and fast production structure to adapt to the rapidly changing market conditions in the industry. However, since the current planning efforts are insufficient, the goal is to develop a dynamic production program that increases efficiency and ensures customer satisfaction. Within the scope of the study, short- and long-term production plans were created, and an AI-supported system was used to make the process dynamic, taking into account urgent orders and unexpected changes in the production line. At this point, it was demonstrated that dynamic production planning was successful in the production process with the transition to a system supported by Industry 4.0 technologies, and some recommendations were made for the production process in the company.

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the most important goals of businesses today is to manage orders quickly, completely and accurately. Order management works to ensure that products are delivered on time, in the right numbers and in good quality. In this respect it is necessary to have a good production plan to manage orders. The basis of a good production plan is a good understanding of the requirements of production.

The mission of production planning is to ensure the availability of scarce resources such as manpower, materials and machinery required for production at the desired location and time in the desired quantity; to ensure the effective and efficient use of these resources [1]. Basically, production planning minimizes the uncertainties that the enterprise may encounter in the production process by determining what, when, how much and with what resources will be produced. In this context, an accurate production plan reduces inventory costs, shortens delivery times and increases customer satisfaction. Production planning methods can be effective under fixed and predictable production conditions based on certain assumptions. With the digital technologies offered by Industry 4.0, production planning has become more flexible, data-driven and dynamic. This situation has necessitated dynamic production planning approaches.

The dynamic and ever-changing nature of production requires the dynamism of the plan and program to be in this structure. Dynamic production planning requires having a plan that requires instant reaction to the situations experienced in the production process and that will adapt to all the situations required at that moment.

Dynamic planning goes beyond static and linear planning models, enabling businesses to quickly adapt to rapidly changing market conditions. This strategy aims to respond more effectively to changing demands and market dynamics beyond traditional planning processes [2]. In such systems, it is critical that the decision-making process is carried out quickly and accurately. In the literature, studies about dynamic production planning are generally carried out with different artificial intelligence methods. Generally, agent based methods are used however we used expert systems.

In a customer-oriented elevator company, the wide product range and rapidly changing market conditions caused by industry dynamics have led the company to a flexible and fast production system structure. A new plan was needed due to the inadequacy of planning and scheduling approaches according to the existing system structure and the concept of unhappy customers. It is aimed to manage the production in the elevator company, which provides the production of special customer orders with variable demands, short delivery times and high variety of products provided by the company, with the correct planning of production. At this stage, it was decided to make a dynamic production planning in order to provide flexibility by increasing efficiency, which is one of the main objectives of Industry 4.0, and to achieve a customer-oriented process. Next, a literature review on production planning and dynamic production planning will be presented. Then, information on artificial intelligence and expert systems will be provided. In the following application section, due to the inadequacy of the plan made within the company, a dynamic production plan will be required using the advanced chaining expert systems method, and this plan will be presented.

2 LITERATURE RESEARCH

2.1 Linear and Dynamic Programming Based Approaches

Linear and dynamic programming methods are widely used in production planning to maximize profits or minimize inventory with limited resources.

In another study, the importance of production planning for businesses was emphasized, and linear programming, one of the techniques used to solve problems in this area, was examined and applied to a clothing business. The mathematical model of the production planning problem for a clothing company that operates based on orders and produces products of various qualities was created using the linear programming approach with numerical data on its limited resources (machinery, labor, raw materials). By solving the mathematical model using the WinQSB 1.0 software package, it was concluded that the objective function of maximizing profit could be achieved by producing a single product type or by accepting more orders [3]. While this study demonstrates

that linear models are suitable for environments with limited variables, it does not adequately address dynamic elements such as demand variability and operational flexibility.

Another study examines production-inventory planning in high-tech, low-volume production supply chains, where long delivery times, intertwined network structures, multiple capacity constraints, and volatile demand and supply uncertainties complicate production and safety stock holding decisions. By following a rapid market entry strategy, they plan to launch a new product while considering the interdependent demand and supply uncertainties arising from risks in technology development [4]. While this study model is sufficient in scope, the accuracy of parameters in real systems is critical.

In another study, efficient production planning in the nylon industry requires the integration of innovation and advancement applications, particularly the use of recycled nylon. This study proposes a new Data-Driven Rolling Horizon Planning (DRHP) approach for an environmentally friendly and dynamic production plan in the plastics industry. Significant reductions of up to 80% in production costs were achieved using the proposed DRHP approach. The findings highlight the power of the proposed DRHP approach in reducing challenges related to inventory and late orders [5]. While this study offers important contributions to environmentally sustainable planning, it also presents challenges such as the need for real-time data integration.

2.2 Flexible Production and Sequencing Strategies

In one study, in addition to evaluating flexibility in production planning, a methodology was presented for evaluating demand-driven flexibility in planning the sequencing of production processes in serial production. This methodology enables the determination of the optimal sequencing of production processes and thus reduces complexity in production planning. A case study was presented to support the explanation of the methodology's steps and verify its applicability [6]. The study did not explain how it would be applied in short-cycle production systems.

In another study, organizing the material flow between production units according to pull system principles is one of the preferred practices instead of creating a production plan. Simulation modeling (Promodel) was used as the testing method. By applying the developed sorting algorithms to the production system, both inventory levels and production interruptions can be effectively managed; thus, a flexible pull system that is dynamic, responsive to demand fluctuations, and closer to low-inventory production targets has been achieved [7]. The missing part of this study concerns how it would respond to real-time demand changes. Since this is a simulation study, this part is not included in the study.

In another study, a balanced production line capable of producing four models was physically designed and installed; in-line flow and labor efficiency were optimized. Standard Job Description Forms were prepared, daily planning was provided with a decision support system, and the production flow was simplified. With the establishment of the production line, cycle time was reduced, production capacity was increased, and customer demands were met on time. The developed method offers an applicable solution for multi-model production lines with high variation, thereby enhancing the company's competitive strength [8]. However, the applicability of this method in different sectors has not been tested. Most of these studies focus on what to do in a single situation and therefore do not provide information on what will happen in different scenarios.

2.3 Strategic Management and Digitalization-Focused Approach

The study conducted by Atagül and colleagues revealed that dynamic planning and workflow management are critical to the competitiveness and sustainable success of businesses. When supported by elements such as technological infrastructure and change management, these strategies facilitate adaptation to rapidly changing business conditions, increase process efficiency, and create a competitive advantage [2].

This study, which offers a strategic approach, emphasizes digitalization and easy adaptation to change. However, issues such as how these strategies will be integrated into production planning systems and tested have not been detailed. None of these studies mention how flexible strategy studies will be conducted under conditions of uncertainty. The application will focus on flexible dynamic planning in the event of changes.

In the study to be implemented, the production plan used in an elevator company's production site is subject to changes based on specific scenarios. For example, when the urgency of an order changes, a machine breaks down, the workforce decreases, or any revisions are made, the planning must be re-planned. This highlights the importance of taking immediate action on production plans. For this study, it was deemed beneficial to utilize an expert system, one of the artificial intelligence techniques, when creating a dynamic production plan. With the AI-supported system, instead of the standard production plan, the production plan to be implemented will be determined based on feedback received from experts, using expert systems.

3 EXPERT SYSTEMS

In this study, the production plan used in the production area of an elevator company undergoes changes in certain scenarios. For example, when the urgency of an order changes, when the machine breaks down, when the labor force decreases, when any revision is made, the planning needs to be done again. In this case, the importance of taking instant action in production plans emerges. While creating a dynamic production plan, it was thought that it would be useful to utilize artificial intelligence techniques for this study. Thanks to the artificial intelligence-supported system, the production plan that should be applied as a result of the feedback from experts instead of the production plan normally used will be revealed with expert systems.

3.1 Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence is defined as the ability of computers or technological systems to perform complex mental processes such as thinking, understanding, generating solutions, inferring meaning, and learning from past experiences [9]. Popov defines artificial intelligence as an effort to get computers to do the work performed by humans [10]. As can be seen, the definitions of each scientist for artificial intelligence are different. Artificial intelligence, in its most general definition, is a set of systems that can imitate human mental abilities and constantly improve itself based on its experiences. The main element that distinguishes this technology from other digital systems is that it can not only process data but also produce meaningful responses to environmental factors. These systems evaluate the situations they encounter from various angles and analyze them according to predetermined criteria. The data obtained is then processed in fast and repetitive ways through algorithms with high processing capacity. In this way, artificial intelligence both makes sense of the data related to the current situation and reinforces the information it has acquired so that it can use it more effectively

in the next process. Following the general definitions of artificial intelligence, expert systems, one of the subfields of artificial intelligence to be used in the application, will be explained.

3.2 Components of Expert Systems

Expert systems are one of the important subfields of artificial intelligence. These systems can be defined as structures that aim to use the knowledge and experience of one or more experts in a computer environment to solve a specific problem [11]. These systems, which imitate the way of thinking of experts in their field, are always considered as consultant computer programs that perform knowledge-based processing [12]. By working on a knowledge-based basis, it makes suggestions on certain issues, provides support for decision-making processes, and can perform more detailed analysis by posing questions to the user when necessary.

Basically, the general functioning structure of these artificial intelligence systems, which work by taking an expert as a model and have the capacity to provide consultancy, consists of user, user interface, knowledge base and inference mechanism.

Figure 1:Expert system structure [13]

The figure above shows the general structure of expert systems. It illustrates how the user, inference mechanism, knowledge base, and expert are positioned structurally.

3.2.1 Experts

A user is someone who uses an expert system. Depending on where an expert system is used and who it is designed for, the people who use it are referred to as users.

3.2.2 Knowledge Base

The knowledge base contains relevant domain knowledge. The most popular current approach to creating expert systems is the rule-based system. In a rule-based system, the knowledge base contains a set of rules [14]. Rules define the facts and relationships within an expert system. Rules are typically structured as IF-THEN statements. The first sentence is the condition, and the second sentence is the consequence. First, the first condition occurs, then the second condition occurs [15].

3.2.3 Inference Engine

The inference engine is software that provides the logical process used by the expert system to access results using the data and capabilities it possesses [14]. The inference engine constitutes the

part of the algorithm that uses the rules, facts, and all information in the knowledge base to arrive at a conclusion.

In expert systems, information and rules are evaluated using two different methods. These methods, referred to as inference methods, are classified as forward (data-based) and backward (goal-based) [16].

3.2.3.1 Forward Chaining Method

The aim of this method is to reach the result starting from the beginning. This method is applied using inductive reasoning. Here, the “if” part checks whether all conditions are met, and the ‘then’ part specifies the result according to these conditions. The “if” part matches the database and is added to the result. Here, each rule is checked once, and the process ends when there are no more rules to check [16].

3.2.3.2 Backward Chaining Method

The purpose of this method is to check the information provided, starting from the final judgment. Deduction is applied in this method. The system starts with the “then” part of the result and reaches the solution by processing all the “if” conditions. The ‘then’ part is matched with the target, and if the “if” part also matches the data, the end is reached [16].

In addition to forward and backward inference methods, another approach in expert systems is tree search methods. In this method, the decision process branches from the root node to the leaf nodes and reaches the final result.

3.2.4 User Interface

The user interface is an important component that uses the expert system and interacts with it continuously [17]. This interaction can be carried out as natural language interaction, graphical interaction, or question-answer interaction. In an expert system, the user interface enables the system to communicate with the user and provides the user with information about the solution process carried out by the system's inference mechanism [15]

Expert systems have a wide range of benefits according to the field in which they are used. These are listed as follows [18].

- Productivity increase: Expert systems work faster than human beings and therefore require less manpower and less wages. As a result, the use of expert systems leads to increased productivity.
- Quality improvement: Expert systems contribute to system quality by producing consistent and appropriate results.
- Consistency: An expert may make a mistake or miss an important detail about the topic under consideration. However, if the expert advances the system correctly, he/she reaches the appropriate conclusion by reviewing all the details on the subject.

- Flexibility: Expert systems are flexible. Knowledge bases can be updated.
- Comprehensiveness: It is impossible for more than one expert to agree on a subject. However, expert knowledge from more than one expert can be combined with the help of expert systems.
- Reduced decision-making time: The decision-making time of expert systems is shorter than that of experts.
- Reliability: Expert systems are computer programs that run very fast. During this time, they reach reliable results because they use the information in the knowledge base.

As can be seen, expert systems make it possible to make accurate, fast and reliable decisions by combining human expertise with the power of artificial intelligence.

4 APPLICATION

The company is located in Organized Industrial Zone, is a pioneer in the elevator industry with the production of automatic doors, cabins and complete elevator systems. On an annual basis, automatic doors, cabins, in-shaft components are produced, as well as other components such as machine motors and control panels. It exports to more than 65 countries.

4.1 The Company's Current Production Planning Process

The elevator company where the application will be implemented uses an ERP system powered by SAP software. Orders are opened daily by the sales unit, and a deadline is selected when these orders are opened. Daily orders are opened at night, and the MRP system reduces the orders and requests planned for the next day. While this system is running, safety stocks and product quantities in warehouses are calculated, and planned orders are created. These planned orders are transferred to the production site as work orders under the control of the production planning team. According to the internal production plan, the progress of these tasks and the implementation of the production plan are monitored on site. The production plan provided to the site by the production planning team is structured so that the delivery date is transferred directly from old to new.

4.2 Identified Problems and Purpose of the Research

While work is being carried out according to the plan being followed on site, situations arise where urgent orders are received at short notice and it is necessary to prioritize these orders over the plan. Due to such situations, production plans change on the spot. However, it is not just a single change but multiple changes occurring simultaneously, leading to a complete overhaul of the production flow. Being able to respond quickly to such situations and satisfy the customer is crucial for the company's reputation. In this regard, there is a need for a dynamic production plan.

The actively used production plan consists of a planning that continues based on the delivery dates of the orders and shows what needs to be done day by day before that delivery date. However, since production is not carried out by working with stocks, some situations arise instantaneously in production. For example, when a machine breaks down, or when there is a delay for any product, or

when order priorities are changed by certain people, the production plan is interrupted. In such a case, a new production plan is needed. Since this planning requires instantaneous intervention, it provides the need for a dynamic production plan. This comprehensive production plan will be transformed into a dynamic production plan. This work will be carried out using expert systems. Because the company where the application is being implemented has been operating since 1977, it was decided to utilize expert systems, leveraging their expert knowledge and experience.

The elevator landing doors section was selected for the part to be examined and applied in the company. Elevator landing doors are the doors located on each floor of the elevator and provide the passage between the elevator car and the building floors. These doors, which are usually opened and closed automatically, allow elevator users to get on and off safely. There are different types of doors in the company. However, in this study, four types of doors will be studied according to the orders in production. These are: E01 Floor Door, C01 Floor Door, B01 Floor Door, Semi Automatic Door.

The initials of the doors will be used for each product in the following work plan. The company has a certain range of customers both in Türkiye and abroad. Since the relevant customer names cannot be shared, domestic and international customers will be accepted.

4.3 Dynamic Production Planning Application with Expert System Approach

When the orders opened by the sales units in the company were examined, the following plan was communicated to the field. 25 E01 floor doors, 200 C01 floor doors, 125 B01 floor doors and 250 slam doors will be produced. After the delivery dates control according to the number of these orders; 20E-50C-25B-150Ç-5E-150C-100Ç-100B will be produced. This order creates individual customers. There are 8 different customers. And these numbers make up the production numbers for each day.

Table 1: Weekly Production Plan

ORDER QUANTITY	PRODUCT	CUSTOMER	DAY	COEFFICIENT	TOTAL WEIGHT
20	E01 Door	Domestic	1	0.5	10,00
50	C01 Door	Foreign	2	1	50,00
25	B01 Door	Domestic	3	0.7	17,50
150	Slamming Door	Foreign	4	1.2	180,00
5	E01 Door	Domestic	5	0.5	12,50
150	C01 Door	Foreign	6	1	150,00
100	Slamming Door	Foreign	7	1.2	120,00
100	B01 Door	Domestic	8	0.7	70,00

While production was to be carried out in this manner, a change was required in the overall order. Managers of different units stated that the urgency of their orders had changed and that the orders needed to be brought forward. Due to the urgent order requests from different unit managers,

traditional production planning methods proved insufficient; therefore, a transition was made to an expert system structure in order to manage the process in a more flexible, information-based, and systematic manner. Here, decisions were made using a forward chaining method, starting with data entry and proceeding step by step according to rules. The reason for choosing the forward chaining method was that the system started with a plan and reached a final decision by applying rules in sequence according to that plan. At the same time, a decision tree structure was used to follow each rule in sequence. This structure was created using the Clixpert interface.

In this study, 5 different experts were selected. These are the people in the company who have all the details about orders: Production manager, General Manager, Domestic sales specialist, Overseas sales specialist and production planning engineer.

There are some comments regarding the orders of these five specialists. The production manager requests that 25 B01 floor doors belonging to a domestic customer be added to the second day. The general manager requests that 150 C01 floor doors belonging to an international customer be pulled on the fourth day. The domestic sales specialist requests that 100 B01 floor doors belonging to his customer be pulled on the fifth day. The international sales specialist requests that 100 impact doors belonging to international customers be pulled on the sixth day. The production planning engineer requests that the normal plan continue according to the delivery order. Within the scope of these requests, the relevant part's delivery options were transferred to the Clixpert departments. The order process began there.

4.4 Application Outputs

Based on expert opinions, the use of Clixpert tools, a forward-chaining method in expert systems with artificial intelligence technologies, is an accepted program. A decision tree was created and systematic planning was conducted [19]. Some questions were asked and answers were requested. The image is as follows:

Figure 2:Decision tree output

It must be explained in the given format. The first question here is whether there will be a change. If so, who will make the request? Questions are asked using an "If-Then" structure. For example, what happens when determining the brightness of a 25B transaction? If the order is placed in the evening, the 50C order will be delayed by one day. If the answer is no, a new expert problem arises. Here, a decision tree is created based on the positive situation, with the rise of five different experts. Clixpert then directs this information to the individual, and a plan is developed.

Table 2:Created New Dynamic Production Plan

ORDER Quantity	Product	Customer	Day	Expected Return	Expected Loss	Expected Value
20	E01 Door	Domestic	1	120	0	120
25	B01 Door	Domestic	2	90	60	30
50	C01 Door	Foreign	3	30	60	-30
150	C01 Door	Foreign	4	160	190	-30
100	B01 Door	Domestic	5	180	120	60
100	Slamming Door	Foreign	6	100	40	60
150	Slamming Door	Foreign	7	60	140	-80
5	E01 Door	Domestic	8	90	120	-30

Table 1 shows the orders for each day in the production plan and their multiples for the relevant product. The relevant coefficients are the coefficients determined by the company on a product basis. The total weight of the produced orders was calculated using these coefficients. The new dynamic plan, which revealed that the relevant information was not recorded in the shell program using the Clixpert software in expert systems, appears in Table 2. It shows what will be produced each day for the relevant orders in the new situation. Additionally, the digital feedback from experts shows what customer-related losses and gains you will experience with this new situation. Here, when an order is brought forward, the positive feedback from experts regarding the order's preparation time due to critical deadlines is shown, as well as the loss from the new plan, which is the loss if another order is placed in the background instead of that order. The net value is revealed by subtracting the expected loss from the numerical net expected return. This value is calculated as 100 points. It is seen that the dynamic production plan, related to technology for the entire week's plan, has a benefit. This improvement rate is as follows:

$$\text{Improvement rate(\%)} = \frac{100}{610} \times 100 = 16,39\%$$

Here, 610 is the total weight taken from Table 1. 100 is the net value score calculated in Table 2. As a result of the dynamic production plan implemented through expert systems, some daily losses are experienced due to order changes, but at the end of the week, 100 points are combined and within the framework of this weighted structure, 16.39%.

Earnings per unit of product in an order $\frac{100}{610}=0,163$. Since there was a 0 point contribution in the first plan, now there is a 0.163 Point contribution per product. Earnings per unit order will be $\frac{100}{8}$ points/orders. Each order is now 12.5 points more productive on average.

4.5 Benefits of the Application

When the production plan used in the field is changed following the instant feedback after the relevant study, the belief and satisfaction of the relevant customers in our company increases. As a result of such situations, it is observed that the number of orders from that customer also increases. In this way, both the company wins and there are no problems in the feedback of each expert opinion holder to their own customers.

When the production plan used in the field was changed with immediate feedback after the relevant work, the relevant center's confidence and speed increased. By extending critical orders to the desired timeframe, customer perspectives were taken into account. These conditions not only fostered a positive vision for the company's customers but also strengthened their ownership of the process, from the details of relevant events to the details. At the same time, production quality was also enhanced. The system is now more adaptable, as the plan can be revised based on expert requests.

5 CONCLUSION

In this study, the effects of instantaneous changes in the production environment on the production plan are discussed. If the orders are produced on the day the customer wants as predicted, the customer is satisfied and the sense of trust in the company increases. Perhaps, with this sense of trust, the same customer may then direct different orders to their salespeople, resulting in an increase in orders. The fact that the feedback from each expert and the actions taken instantly regarding the orders are solved with the decision tree in expert systems reveals that the decision tree can be controlled in case of any crisis. Since the changes in orders are managed systematically, there is no confusion in the production lines. This saves time and cost for the company. Finally, thanks to its structure, this decision tree can serve as a case study for similar decisions in the future.

Unlike other literature, the application utilized an expert system based on the opinions of company experts. This study found that integrating expert opinions from AI techniques into expert systems in production planning resulted in a 16.39% improvement in customer satisfaction and decision-making. Based on feedback from experts on order details, a 25% increase in the number of orders was observed after these orders were delivered. In addition, the study shows that it has a contribution of 0.163 points. An average contribution of 12.5 points was obtained per order.

Future studies could utilize this system for similar decisions in different sectors and areas using this decision tree structure. Instead of the one-week plan used in this study, the system could be converted to dynamic planning by increasing order numbers based on customer requests. The system's performance could be tested by adding conditions such as high demand, capacity constraints, and inventory in different scenarios. This study could also measure the stability of the model.

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